

1 Context

The Agroforestry Living Lab (LL) in Germany focused on agroforestry (AF) in Brandenburg, centred around DeFAF's main office in Cottbus (Figure 1). As this region has many agricultural areas with unfavourable natural site conditions, e.g. with regard to soil type, water retention capacity, and susceptibility to erosion, conventional arable farming cannot guarantee sufficient protection of the resources soil, water, and biodiversity. These protected natural assets can therefore be enhanced by the establishment of agroforestry systems (AFS). At the same time, the LL Brandenburg is one of the regions in Germany most affected by the climate crisis, so AFS can be expected to have a particularly positive effect here.

DeFAF maintains intensive and regular contact with the stakeholders and organised various events. These range from farm days, presentations, and participation in trade fairs to cultural events such as celebrating a cinema evening. In the course of the project, the main focus was on the further development and testing of digital tools in the field of AF. There was a good level of interest in this. The group members fluctuated and is characterised by different intensities of participation, depending on interest and the time budget available. Regular information on the project DIGITAF and activities in the LL where communicated through a project dedicated subpage on DeFAF's Website www.agroforst-info.de/digitaf, including an activity slider, reports and briefings (e.g. Hübner, 2024), and invitations via mail.

Figure 1. The DE Living Lab Brandenburg with the location of key LL sites and institutions.

Domin's Farm situated in the very south of Brandenburg is reported to be one of the first AF farms in Germany. Thomas Domin planted the first AFS in 2015 in the form of seven alley cropping strips on arable land (about 5 hectares), mainly with poplar for energy production. In 2016, two strips (1 ha) on permanent grassland completed the system. In 2020, the AFS was expanded by three additional woody strips (about 2 ha) on arable land with mixed woody plants and shrubs. An orchard system funded as a compensation measure as well as rows of fruit trees along former roads have recently been added.

ZGJ Landwirtschafts GmbH is based in southern Brandenburg, situated between Calau and Luckau in the Oberspreewald-Lausitz district. Robert Häussler farms a total of approximately 1,400 hectares across three production sites. As this region receives an average of only 540 mm of rainfall, the cultivation of alfalfa – which is comparatively drought-tolerant – has become established as a feed crop.

Other crops include cereals (rye, barley, triticale, wheat and oats) as well as sunflowers, rapeseed, silage maize and grain maize. Alongside the cultivation of market crops, forage production is a high priority, as the farm keeps 340 dairy cows. In 2020, several tree strips for poultry farming in AFS were established on the farm's arable land, which were expanded by adding individual trees for timber production. An alley cropping with poplar was established in 2025, now among the largest AFS in Brandenburg.

Wilmar's Gardens, run by manager Maria Giménez, specialises in planting trees and shrubs along contour lines to improve water retention and the microclimate in this arid landscape, characterised by sandy soils low in organic matter. Various fruit trees, such as apple and quince, have been planted in an AFS. While the alleys are being grazed by cattle, there are also future plans to utilise the timber from the trees. A 45-hectare silvoarable AFS has also been established, featuring strips of poplars arranged in four rows. The distance between the strips of trees is 30 metres. The system is very easy to manage and is particularly suitable for applications in larger plots. The biomass is to be harvested after 10 years and used as timber or wood chips. The farm also operates a market garden, which has been expanded to 5 hectares. Various vegetable varieties are produced and sold at market stalls or to the catering industry.

Rainer Guhl manages a 650-hectare **Landwirtschaftsbetrieb Düpow** near Perleberg in the Prignitz district in the north-west of Brandenburg. The farms soils range from sandy to loamy sand with an average soil quality of 30 points, and the area receives approximately 550 mm of rainfall. The farmer cultivates winter and spring cereals, rapeseed, maize, starch potatoes, sugar beets, and sunflowers. Since 2020, three AFS with poplars were established, covering 88 hectares in total AFS-size, from which 10.8 hectares are trees (2020: 8 ha AFS with 1.8 ha tree area; 2023: 60 ha AFS with 6.5 ha tree area, 2024 on grassland: 20 ha AFS with 2.5 ha tree area).

2 DIGITAF Brandenburg Living Lab (LL BB) – activities by year

2022

24 June 2022 – Hearing of the German Bioeconomy Council: The as part of the work of DeFAF in the BB LL was the participation in a hearing of the German Bioeconomy Council. The event brought together 11 participants and provided an opportunity to discuss the role of AFS within the broader context of Germany's bioeconomy strategy. The hearing contributed to stakeholder engagement and strengthened links between AF practitioners, policymakers, and bioeconomy experts.

26 June 2022 – Orchard Excursion Old Fruit Varieties Selected for Yield: An orchard excursion was organized by DeFAF focusing on traditional fruit varieties and their potential contribution to resilient agricultural systems (Figure 2). Approximately 20 participants met with Hans-Joachim Bannier, one of Germany's leading experts on old apple and sweet cherry varieties. The excursion highlighted the importance of genetic diversity, regional fruit heritage, and sustainable orchard management.

Figure 2. Hans-Joachim Bannier explains fruit orchards.

5–7 July 2022 – *Agroforestry Summer Excursion in Brandenburg*: DeFAF organized a three-day AF summer excursion with approximately 40 participants, that changed during the days as one-day participation was favoured. The excursion visited four exemplary AF farms that form the core of the BB LL (LL-Kick Off) (Figure 3): a) Thomas Domin Farm, Peickwitz, b) Landwirtschaftshof Düpow, 3) Schlossgut Alt Madlitz (Benedikt Bösel), Briesen (Mark), 4) ZGJ Landwirtschafts GmbH, Zinnitz near Calau. The excursion provided practical insights into different AF approaches, farm management strategies, ecosystem services, and opportunities for integrating trees into agricultural production systems. In addition, an Agroforestry Regulars’ Table was organized with approximately 30 participants, facilitating networking and knowledge exchange among practitioners, researchers, and stakeholders. The activity was implemented within DIGITAF and in cooperation with AF and agri-environmental measure (AUKM) initiatives.

a) Thomas Domin Farm, Peickwitz.

b) Landwirtschaftshof Düpow.

c) Schlossgut Alt Madlitz, Briesen.

d) ZGJ Landwirtschafts GmbH, Zinnitz.

Figure 3. Agroforestry Summer Excursion in Brandenburg.

11 July 2022 – *University of Kassel Lecture: Soil Carbon Sequestration in Agroforestry Systems*: A guest lecture was delivered at the University of Kassel, Department of Ecological Agricultural Sciences, from 10:00 to 12:00. The lecture formed part of the module „Soil Fertility and Nutrient Cycles” and focused on soil carbon sequestration in AFS. The presentation examined how agroforestry contributes to improved soil fertility, nutrient cycling, and long-term carbon storage. Participants from a parallel module also attended, allowing a comparison between agroforestry-based and compost-based approaches to soil carbon enhancement.

6–8 September 2022 – *DIGITAF Project Kick-Off Meeting, Montpellier, France*: Representatives of the BB LL participated in the official DIGITAF Kick-Off Meeting held at PP INRAE in Montpellier, France. The event brought together DIGITAF partners from across Europe to establish the project’s framework, discuss LL methodologies, coordinate work packages, and define future cooperation activities. Field visits completed the programme (Figure 4). The meeting marked

a) Domaine du Chapitre, Ville-neuve-lès-Maguelone, FR.

b) Project meeting INRAE, Montpellier, FR.

Figure 4. DIGITAF Project Kick-Off Meeting and farm visits, Montpellier, France.

the formal start of the DIGITAF project and laid the foundation for collaboration among participating regions.

On September 4, 2022, a field day was held at Wilmars Gaerten on the topic of „Creating Climate-Resilient Landscapes with Agroforestry and Keyline Design” North of Berlin. The field day was organized by Netzwerk-Wasser-Agri in collaboration with BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg. Over 20 participants toured Maria Giménez’s AF plots (Figure 5).

a) Maria Giménez explains the key-line systems.

b) Alley cropping system with poplar.

Figure 5. Field day at Wilmars Gaerten in Märkisch Wilmersdorf.

September 2022 – National Biomass Strategy Stakeholder Participation: The BB LL was part of the stakeholder participation activities related to Germany's National Biomass Strategy. Information was exchanged with representatives of the German Bioeconomy Council and the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV), including Katharina Schwarz. These exchanges ensured that AF perspectives were considered within discussions on sustainable biomass production and bioeconomy development.

Autumn/Winter 2022 – DIGITAF Communication and Filming Activities: Filming activities were initiated as part of DIGITAF communication and dissemination efforts. Recordings were undertaken at several AF sites, including Volkertshaus in Baden-Württemberg and locations in France (Figure 6). The film “Mit Bäumen gegen die Dürre – Wie Agroforstwirtschaft unsere Felder schützt” Series 925 (32 min.) by ARTE-RE was broadcasted on German TV more than seven times. The BR film in the series DokThema “Ackern unter Bäumen – Landwirte entdecken den Agroforst” is available on youtube and the ARD Mediathek. Both films support project communication, stakeholder engagement, and the development of educational and promotional content showcasing innovative AFS across Europe. It was also shown on CZ TV.

Figure 6. Screenshot of film in ARTE and BR TV.

7 November 2022 – Field Day: Agroforestry Systems for More Nature and Climate Protection: A field day entitled „Agroforestry Systems for More Nature and Climate Protection” was organized at the LL farms. The event focused on practical examples of agroforestry implementation and their contribution to biodiversity enhancement, climate adaptation, and sustainable land management. Hosted by LL farmers Thomas Domin and Robert Häussler, the field day included demonstrations and discussions at locations in Peickwitz and Groß Jehser. Participants explored how AFS can simultaneously support agricultural productivity, ecosystem services, and climate protection objectives.

Figure 7. Overview of activities 2022

Summary 2022: Throughout 2022, the BB LL successfully launched its activities within the DIGITAF project. Key achievements included the organization of the online questionnaires among members of the LL and across DE with 90 participants in a second round, which later resulted in a publication by Tranchina et al. (2024), but also practical field excursions, scientific outreach through university teaching, participation in European project coordination, stakeholder engagement on bioeconomy and biomass strategies, communication activities, and demonstration events showcasing AF solutions. These activities strengthened regional and international networks while promoting AF as an important tool for climate resilience, biodiversity conservation, and sustainable agricultural development.

2023

January 2023 – 16th Future Forum for Rural Development, International Green Week, Berlin: The BB LL members participated in the „Future Forum for Rural Development“ during the International Green Week in Berlin (Figure 8). Within the expert forum entitled „Trees in the Fields? Agroforestry as a Climate Opportunity!“, the contribution „Climate Protection: The Potential of Agroforestry Systems“ highlighted the role of AF in climate mitigation and adaptation. The event provided a platform for dialogue between policymakers, practitioners, researchers, and stakeholders regarding the integration of trees into agricultural landscapes. Workshop results were also published by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture (BMLEH, 2023).

Figure 8. LL Members in Berlin at the International Green Week (Author: JG).

7–9 March 2023 – Landcare Europe Workshop, Jaén, Andalusia, Spain: Representatives of the BB LL participated in the Landcare Europe workshop entitled „Agroforestry Systems to Improve Biodiversity, Water & Soil Management and Economic Viability in and outside Natura 2000 Areas.“ The presentation „Ecological and Economic Benefits of Traditional and Modern Agroforestry Systems“ showcased AF as an effective approach to combine environmental objectives with farm profitability. The workshop facilitated international exchange on AF practices and policy frameworks.

10 March 2023 – Agriculture and Climate Crisis Conference, Berlin: At the VKU Forum in Berlin, the DeFAF contributed to the event „Water – A Scarce Resource?“ organized by MEP Martin Häusling. The presentation „With Trees against Drought – How Agroforestry Can Protect Our Fields“ demonstrated how AFS enhance water retention, reduce wind erosion, and increase climate resilience in agricultural landscapes.

4 May 2023 – *Experimental application of biochar*: As one of the activities to evaluate the effect of the application of biochar, experiments were carried out on the silvoarable plot of the LL farm in collaboration with BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg (Figure 9).

a) Sometimes researcher get to drive machines for the experiments.

b) Different amounts of biochar were applied by hand in the silvoarable AFS at Domin's Farm.

Figure 9. Experiments with biochar application to monitor soil properties at the LL Farm.

6–8 June 2023 – *DIGITAF Consortium Meeting, Agroscope Zurich, CH*: DeFAF participated in the DIGITAF Consortium Meeting hosted by Agroscope in Zurich, CH, including a field trip to AF sites. Contributions focused on the development of an „Agroforestry Map of Europe“ and discussions on advancing the map from a basic visualization tool towards a comprehensive European AF database. The meeting strengthened collaboration among DIGITAF partners and supported the development of digital tools for AF planning and monitoring.

16 August 2023 – *Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology, Köllitsch, SN*: A presentation on the activities of DeFAF and the establishment of the International Network for Agroforestry Systems (INAS) was delivered at the Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology (Figure 10). The event facilitated networking and knowledge exchange between AF stakeholders in Germany.

a) Group picture in front of the Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology. (Source: LFULG)

b) Field trip in the Lom-matscher Pflege.

Figure 10. International Network for Agroforestry Systems (INAS) at the Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology, Köllitsch.

4 September 2023 – *Field Visit at Landwirtschaftshof Düpow*: A field visit was organized at Landwirtschaftshof Düpow, one of Brandenburg's pioneering AF farms. Farm manager Rainer Guhl presented practical experiences with shelterbelts and AFS that reduce the impact of increasingly dry summer winds. During the field walk, participants discussed the contribution of AF to climate adaptation, crop productivity, and resilience. The event was held under the title „Agroforestry – An Insurance against Climate Change? Experiences from Brandenburg and Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania.“

6 September 2023 – 134th VDLUFA Congress, Freising-Weihenstephan, BY: At the VDLUFA Congress on „Climate Adaptation and Food Security – A Challenge for Agriculture“, DeFAF presented „Agroforestry for Climate Adaptation and Food Security – Findings from Research and How We Deal with Them.“ to a large audience of about 200 persons (Figure 11). The contribution summarized scientific evidence on AF benefits and discussed practical implementation challenges and opportunities.

Figure 11. VD LUFA conference in Weihenstephan.

12 September 2023 – Agroforestry in Armenia (Online): DeFAF contributed to an international online event on AF in Armenia with the presentation „Climate Remediation and Adaptation through Agroforestry – How Agroforestry Can Protect Our Fields!“ The presentation highlighted the potential of AFS to improve resilience against climate change and support sustainable land management in different climatic regions.

12 September 2023 – Expert Dialogue on Agroforestry and Nature Conservation, Märkisch Wilmsdorf: At the AUKM expert dialogue „Agroforestry – Opportunities and Challenges for Nature Conservation“, DeFAF presented „Agroforestry as an Opportunity for Nature Conservation in Agriculture and Current Challenges – Site Suitability for Agroforestry Establishment in Brandenburg.“ Discussions focused on integrating AF into agri-environmental schemes and biodiversity strategies.

27–28 September 2023 – 9th Forum Agroforestry Systems, Freiburg: DigitAF project actively contributed to the 9th Forum under the theme „Shaping Agriculture for the Future.“ Two EU HE project contributions were presented: 1) „DigitAF: DIGItal Tools to Support Agroforestry – Linking Field and Cloud“ and 2) „ReForest – Agroforestry at the Forefront of Agricultural Sustainability in Multifunctional Landscapes in Europe“. In addition, project posters were presented by consortium members, highlighting progress and results from both DIGITAF and REFOREST. The forum provided a major networking opportunity for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers (Figure 11).

- a) University Freiburg
- b) Excursion to Streuobstparadies Staufen - Johannes Geng
- c) Excursion to Fruit orchards and geese at Hofgut Hochburg, Emmendinge (Photo: JG)
- d) Organising team from DeFAF and Uni Freiburg. (Photo: LB)

Figure 12. Impression from the 9th Forum Agroforestry Systems, Freiburg.

10–11 October 2023 – CDRterra Workshop, Munich: DeFAF participated in the CDRterra workshop „Possible Pathways of Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) in Germany“ at Museum Island, Munich. A Podium Discussion explored the role of land-use systems, including AF, in climate mitigation and carbon removal strategies.

October 2023 – value chain mapping: The value chain mapping was at first constructed on a theoretical base in September 2023 in a second step verified during a farm visit in October 2023 and online meeting with the farmer. In a third step, external or non-direct participants of the value chain were added to the model in December 2023 (Tranchina et al., 2023).

12 October 2023 Expert discussion “Agroforestry: Opportunities and Challenges for Nature Conservation” brings together representatives from the fields of nature conservation and AF at the Conference Centre Seddiner See near Potsdam (Hübner, 2023).

6–8 November 2023 – Agroforestry Academy, Witzenhausen: At the Agroforestry Academy held at DEULA Witzenhausen, the BB LL contributed two training sessions: 1) „FarmTreeTool as a Tool for Agroforestry Planning“ and 2) „Practical Tools and Apps“. The sessions introduced participants to digital decision-support tools developed and promoted within DIGITAF, supporting farm-level AF design and management (*Figure 13*).

Figure 13. Participants of the Agroforestry Academy.

1 December 2023 – Student course in the agroforestry module at Weihenstephan-Triesdorf University of Applied Sciences, Freising: The presentation „Practical Tools and Apps“ was delivered within the framework of the REFOREST and DIGITAF projects. Participants were introduced to digital solutions supporting AF planning, implementation, and monitoring.

6 December 2023 – LL Event at Thomas Domin Farm, Peickwitz: At a LL event hosted by Thomas Domin in Peickwitz, a presentation on „Framework Conditions for the Design of Agroforestry Systems Recognised under Agricultural Funding Law“ was delivered. The contribution focused on legal and policy requirements affecting AF implementation and eligibility for agricultural support schemes. As a result of that workshop, that also marks the annual LL meeting, a value chain was developed which was described in DigitAF Deliverable 3.2 entitled „Schematic Map of the Agroforestry Value Chain for each LL“ (Tranchina et al., 2023).

14 December 2023 – DIGITAF Online Workshop: The BB LL participated in an DIGITAF online workshop dedicated to the presentation of project tools and digital solutions. The workshop enabled project partners to exchange experiences, discuss tool development progress, and identify opportunities for further improvement and stakeholder uptake.

Summary 2023: During 2023, the BB LL significantly expanded its outreach, networking, and dissemination activities within DIGITAF. Activities included participation in European workshops and consortium meetings, scientific conferences, policy dialogues, field demonstrations, and farmer- and advisor-oriented training events. A particular focus was placed on digital tools for AF planning, climate adaptation, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity enhancement. Through these activities, the LL strengthened connections between research, practice, and policy while contributing to the wider adoption of AFS in Germany and across Europe (*Figure 14*).

Figure 14. Overview of activities 2023.

2024

January 2024 – Foundation of a Regenerative Umbrella Organisation (Online): DeFAF contributed a short online presentation introducing the association, its history, and its role in promoting AF in Germany. The presentation supported discussions on establishing a broader regenerative agriculture umbrella organisation and highlighted AF as a key element of regenerative land-use systems.

27 February 2024 – DeFAF Colloquium (Online): Within the regular DeFAF colloquium series, a presentation entitled “DIGITal Tools to boost AgroForestry – Tools and Applications for Agroforestry Planning” introduced the objectives and progress of the DIGITAF project. Participants were informed about the Horizon Europe consortium, which brings together 25 partners from 20 countries, including research institutions, universities, SMEs, NGOs, and international organisations. The event highlighted how digital tools can support agroforestry implementation and decision-making across Europe.

17 April 2024 – Expert Dialogue on Agroforestry Policy Expectations, Seddiner See, Brandenburg: DeFAF organised and facilitated an expert discussion entitled “Expectations of Agroforestry from Agricultural, Environmental and Climate Policy”. The event focused on the implementation of AFS from a nature conservation perspective and brought together experts from administration, research, and practice. Discussions addressed policy barriers and opportunities for AF implementation, as well as its contribution to biodiversity conservation, climate adaptation, and sustainable land management.

16 May 2024 – University lecture at HNE Eberswalde, Brandenburg: A three-hour lecture was delivered within the AF teaching module at the University for Sustainable Development Eberswalde (HNEE). The lecture focused on “Digital Tools in the Planning and Evaluation of Agroforestry Systems” and introduced students to current digital applications developed within the DIGITAF project.

18 June 2024 – Agroforestry in Lusatia: New Pathways for Agriculture, Peickwitz: DeFAF co-organised the final event of the AgroBaLa project together with a stakeholder workshop on sustainability assessment of AFS within the AGROWERT-REGIO initiative. Held at the Thomas Domin demonstration farm in Peickwitz, the event combined practical demonstrations with participatory discussions on evaluating ecological, economic, and social sustainability aspects of AFS. Approximately six hours of presentations, field demonstrations, and stakeholder exchanges contributed to strengthening regional AF

networks. The results of that workshop that also marks the annual LL meeting fed into Deliverable 2.4, which is a roadmap on tools for anticipated benefits and costs of AF innovations (Cumplido-Marin et al., 2025).

22 July 2024 – FAO High-Level Dialogue on Scaling Up Agroforestry (Online): DeFAF participated in the FAO High-Level Dialogue on Scaling Up Agroforestry, an international event dedicated to promoting investments in resilient agrifood systems. Participation enabled the exchange of experiences with global stakeholders and strengthened international visibility of European AF initiatives.

9 September 2024 – Aspen Institute Conference, Berlin: DeFAF participated in the Aspen Institute event “Transatlantic Perspectives on the Digital Transformation of Agriculture.” Discussions focused on opportunities and challenges arising from digitalisation in agriculture and the role of innovative technologies in supporting sustainable farming systems.

17 September 2024 – Landcare Europe General Assembly (Online): DeFAF participated in the first General Assembly of Landcare Europe. Discussions addressed strategic developments within the network and opportunities for future collaboration on sustainable land management and AF initiatives.

18 September 2024 – Preparatory Meeting for the Global Forum for Food and Agriculture (GFFA) 2025: DeFAF participated in the advisory panel preparation meeting for the Global Forum for Food and Agriculture 2025 organised by the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL). The meeting focused on pathways towards a sustainable bioeconomy and provided an opportunity to bring AF perspectives into upcoming international policy discussions.

21 September 2024 – District Harvest Festival, Peickwitz: DeFAF supported the district harvest festival in cooperation with Thomas Domin (Figure 14). Throughout the day, the organisation operated an information stand providing information on AFS, climate adaptation, biodiversity, and the activities of the BB LL. The event reached a broad public audience and contributed to raising awareness of AF among farmers and citizens.

a) Welcome sign to the Kreis-Erntedankfest (District Harvest Moon).

b) Minister president opening ceremony with LL farmer Thomas Domin.

c) DeFAF representation at the festivity.

Figure 15. Impressions from the District Harvest Festival, Peickwitz.

29 September – 2 October 2024 – Landcare Europe Workshop, Pardubice, Czech Republic: DeFAF participated in the Landcare Europe Workshop entitled “Soils as Natural Carbon Sinks – Practical Implementation of Water and Soil Management and Requirements for CAP Measures.” The workshop ex-

amined practical approaches to soil carbon sequestration, water management, and policy implementation under the CAP. Participation facilitated international exchange on climate mitigation and adaptation measures, including the role of AFS.

8 October 2024 – Political Thanksgiving Event, BMEL, Berlin: DeFAF attended the Political Thanksgiving event hosted by the Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (Figure 15). The event provided opportunities for networking and exchange with agricultural stakeholders and policymakers. LL Farmer Thomas Domin received the highest honour for German agriculturists for his engagement for AF by the minister.

Figure 16. Thomas receives the Professor Niklas Medal in Berlin.

10 October 2024 – Brandenburg State Chancellery Workshop, Potsdam: DeFAF participated in the workshop “Utilising Synergies – Implementing the Soil Mission.” Discussions focused on integrating soil protection and restoration objectives into regional and national policy frameworks and highlighted the contribution of AFS to healthy soils.

15 October 2024 – ILVO Flanders Webinar (Online): During the webinar “Farmers with Trees: On the Way to 2035” (“Boeren met bomen: op weg naar 2035”), DeFAF presented the Agroforestry Map of Europe to an audience of approximately 200 participants. The presentation demonstrated how digital mapping tools can support AF planning, monitoring, and knowledge exchange across Europe. For this, two videos with instructions were recorded and made available.

21 October 2024 – Agricultural Associations Platform Meeting, Berlin: DeFAF participated in a meeting of agricultural associations operating under Chatham House Rules. The meeting focused on current agricultural policy developments and opportunities for coordinated stakeholder engagement.

25 October 2024 – Workshop on Digital Tools for Resource-Conserving Soil Management, Potsdam: At the ATB, DeFAF participated in a workshop exploring digital tools for sustainable soil management (Figure 16). Discussions included opportunities for integrating AF-related digital applications into broader land management decision-support systems.

Figure 17. Presentation of a field robot at ATB.

12–14 November 2024 – ILVO Workshop on Economic Tools, Utrecht, Netherlands: DeFAF participated in the DIGITAF workshop hosted by ILVO and presented work on “Digital Tools for Agroforestry Financial Analysis.” The workshop focused on evaluating and comparing digital tools that support economic assessments of AFS. Discussions addressed farm-level decision-making, profitability analyses, and investment planning.

2 December 2024 – German Farmers’ Association (DBV) Arable Farming Committee, Berlin: At short notice, DeFAF represented Thomas Domin and delivered the presentation “What Makes Agroforestry Fit for the Future? Current Balance and Outlook.” The presentation provided an overview of recent developments in agroforestry, discussed current challenges and opportunities, and highlighted future perspectives for integrating AF into mainstream agricultural systems. Presentation materials were subsequently distributed to committee participants.

Figure 18. Overview of activities 2024.

Summary 2024: During 2024, DeFAF continued to strengthen its role as a key intermediary between research, policy, and agricultural practice within the DIG-ITAF project and beyond. Activities covered digital tool development and dissemination, educational outreach, stakeholder engagement, policy dialogue, international cooperation, and Living Lab activities in Brandenburg. Through participation in national and international events, DeFAF contributed to advancing AF as a practical solution for climate adaptation, biodiversity conservation, sustainable soil management, and resilient agricultural production systems.

2025

11 March 2025 – Visit of State Secretary Sylvia Bender, Peickwitz, Brandenburg: The BB LL hosted State Secretary Sylvia Bender of the Brandenburg Ministry of Agriculture, Environment and Climate Protection at the demonstration farm of Thomas Domin in Peickwitz (Figure 17). The visit included a farm tour, discussions on AF implementation in Brandenburg, and a panel discussion involving representatives from practice, administration, and research. The event attracted regional media attention and provided an opportunity to present AF as a practical solution for climate adaptation, biodiversity enhancement, and sustainable agricultural production.

Figure 19. Workshop on AF implementation in Brandenburg at Domin's Farm.

13 March 2025 – European Commission Hearing (Online): DeFAF participated in an online hearing organised by the European Commission in connection with ongoing discussions on AF and sustainable land-use policies. Although technical difficulties limited participation, the event demonstrated the increasing relevance of AF within European policy processes and highlighted the need for continued stakeholder engagement.

2 May 2025 – *Agroforestry Workshop, Schmochtitz, Saxony*: At the invitation of the Saxon State Office for Environment, Agriculture and Geology (LfULG), DeFAF contributed to a workshop dedicated to AFS and their practical implementation. Discussions among about 20 teachers in the “green Jobs” focused on opportunities for integrating AF into teaching of professionals and current developments in policy and advisory services, that need to find their place in curricula (Figure 18).

Figure 20. Entrance sign to the “Bildungsgut Schmochtitz”.

19 May 2025 – *EURAF General Assembly (Online / Brussels)*: DeFAF participated in the General Assembly of the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF). Discussions addressed organisational matters, membership renewal, and ongoing developments concerning the Agroforestry Map of Europe. Particular attention was given to the integration of digital tools and geospatial information developed within DIGITAF.

20 May 2025 – *EU Carbon Farming Workshop, Brussels*: DeFAF attended a European workshop on Carbon Farming and the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF). Discussions focused on the role of AFS in carbon sequestration, monitoring and verification approaches, and future opportunities for farmers to participate in carbon farming schemes.

23 May 2025 – *Saxon Farmers’ Association, Dresden*: DeFAF participated in discussions with the Saxon Farmers’ Association concerning the future development of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The exchange addressed both the current CAP Strategic Plan and possible directions for the post-2027 CAP framework. AF was presented as a multifunctional land-use approach capable of contributing to climate, biodiversity, and production objectives.

25–27 June 2025 – *DIGITAF Consortium Meeting, Cottbus, Peickwitz and Calau*: DeFAF organised the annual DIGITAF Consortium Meeting in Brandenburg. Project partners from across Europe gathered in Cottbus for working sessions, strategic discussions, and knowledge exchange. The programme included field visits to two Brandenburg LL farms (Figure 19) and an excursion to traditional AFS in the Spreewald region. Participants explored practical examples of AF implementation, discussed Living Lab activities, and exchanged experiences regarding the development and application of digital AF tools. The consortium meeting strengthened collaboration among DIGITAF project partners and showcased Brandenburg as a leading region for AF innovation and demonstration in Germany.

Figure 21. Participants of the DIGITAF GA in Peickwitz”.

26–27 September 2025 – *International Czech-German Agroforestry Excursion*: An international excursion involving participants from Germany and the Czech Republic visited the LL BB (Figure 20). The programme included visits to AF farms in the Peickwitz and Calau regions and facilitated cross-border exchange on AF practices, farm management approaches, and policy frameworks. The excursion provided opportunities for practitioners, researchers, advisors, and stakeholders to discuss experiences with AF implementation and to strengthen cooperation between neighbouring regions. Particular emphasis was placed on practical lessons learned from LL farms and the role of AF in climate adaptation and sustainable rural development.

- a) International guests from CZ at the LL Farm Thomas Domin.
- b) At ZGJ Farm we received explanations on silvopastoral AFS with chicken and poplar.
- c) Rainy weather did not stop the group from seeing innovative orchard AFS.

Figure 22. Impressions from the International Czech-German Agroforestry Excursion.

4 October 2025 – Soil Sampling Campaign at the Brandenburg Living Lab, Peickwitz: Another soil sampling campaign was conducted on grassland areas within the Brandenburg Living Lab. The activity aimed to support monitoring and evaluation efforts related to AFS and their impacts on soil quality, carbon storage, and ecosystem services. The collected data will contribute to ongoing research activities within DIGITAF and support the assessment of AF performance under practical farming conditions (den Herder et al., 2026).

Figure 23. Overview of activities 2025.

Summary 2025: In 2025, DeFAF further strengthened its role as a facilitator of AF innovation, stakeholder dialogue, and international cooperation within the DIGITAF project. Key activities included organising the DIGITAF Consortium Meeting in the LL BB, hosting political and stakeholder visits, participating in European discussions on carbon farming and agricultural policy, supporting AF training and knowledge exchange, and

conducting monitoring activities within the BB LL. These efforts contributed to the dissemination of AF knowledge, the advancement of digital decision-support tools, and the promotion of AF as an important component of resilient and sustainable agricultural systems in Germany and Europe.

2026

REFOREST and DIGITAF Final Meetings, Brussels, Belgium: DeFAF participated in the final meetings of the Horizon Europe projects DIGITAF and REFOREST in Brussels. The meetings brought together project partners from across Europe to review project achievements, discuss final outputs, evaluate impacts, and identify opportunities for future collaboration. Particular attention was given to the dissemination and long-term exploitation of project results, including digital decision-support tools, Living Lab experiences, AF databases, policy recommendations, and stakeholder engagement approaches developed during the project period.

13–14 June 2026 – LL final meeting with key stakeholders and the public, Peickwitz, Germany: As part of the official main opening event of the 31st “Brandenburg Landpartie”, which took place at the LL farm in Peickwitz, the DeFAF was represented with a stand and was thus able to inform the public about agroforestry. On Saturday, the Brandenburg Minister for Agriculture, the executive board of the Brandenburg Farmers’ Association, agri-influencers and even the “Erntehoheit”, as well as landowners with their own agroforestry plans, were welcomed at the stand. In addition to information on agroforestry and digital tools, visitors could also follow an educational trail on agroforestry.

Figure 24. LL farmer T. Domin and president and CEO of the Brandenburg Farmers’ Association.

Figure 25. Overview of activities 2026.

June 2026 – European Agroforestry Conference (EURAF 2026), Neuchâtel, Switzerland: DeFAF plans to participate in the European Agroforestry Conference (EURAF 2026) in Neuchâtel, CH, where the concluding meetings will be held. The conference will bring together researchers, farmers, advisors, policymakers, and practitioners from across Europe to exchange knowledge and experiences on AFS. Participation will support the dissemination of results from both the DIGITAF and REFOREST projects, including advances in digital tools, Living Lab methodologies, AF mapping, sustainability assessment, and policy development. The conference will also provide opportunities to strengthen international networks, identify future research and innovation priorities,

and contribute to discussions on the role of AF in addressing climate change, biodiversity loss, sustainable food production, and rural development. The final meetings will provide an opportunity to reflect on lessons learned and to strengthen cooperation among European AF networks beyond the lifetime of the projects.

3 Continuation after the project

Outlook: The year 2026 marks the completion of major European AF projects in which DeFAF has played an active role. Through participation in final project events and international conferences, DeFAF will contribute to ensuring that project results remain accessible and relevant for farmers, advisors, researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders. These activities will help consolidate the knowledge generated through DIGITAF and REFOREST and support the continued expansion of AF across Germany and Europe.

The LL will continue through the continued activities of the various participants who have engaged with DigitAF during the past four years. The systems at Domin's Farm, ZGJ Agrar, Wilmars Gaerten, Landwirtschaftsbetrieb Düpow and several other AFS in Brandenburg will continue to be commercially managed. At DeFAF, a new project from the Agroecology Partnership, called EELAP, will continue the work of the German Associations for Agroforestry with the stakeholders in the BB LL, but also extending its reach to the neighbouring state, of Saxony. DeFAF continues to provide an important forum for AF activities and promotion in Germany and at EURAF, including the promotion of the Agroforestry Map of Europe.

Figure 26. This years' Champagne rye – a traditional cereal variety – thrives at the agroforestry site at sunset at the LL Farm.

4 References

- Cumplido-Marin, L., Burgess, P., Graves, A., Lojka, B., Hübner, R., Mantino, A., Ripamonti, A., Herder, M. d., Thissen, W., Mott, S., Reubens, B., & Carton, S. (2025). *Deliverable 2.4 – Roadmap 2.0 on tools for anticipated benefits and costs of agroforestry innovations*. DigitAF (101059794).
- den Herder, M., Cumplido-Marin, L., Burgess, P. J., Aynekulu, E., Cella, F., Houška, J., Hübner, R., Kay, S., Lojka, B., Mantino, A., Moreno, G., Nauta, S., Palma, J., Pardon, P., Smith, J., Ripamonti, A., Rolo, V., Serra, A., Rønn-Andersen, K.,...Thissen, W. (2026). *Deliverable 3.5 - Methods to Verify and Account for the Carbon and Soil Health Benefits of Agroforestry. Deliverable 3.5 for the DigitAF project*.
- Hübner, R. (2024). *Kurzbericht DigitAF*. <https://agroforst-info.de/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/DIGITAF-Bericht-DeFAF.pdf>
- Tranchina, M., Burgess, P., Cella, F. G., Cumplido-Marin, L., Gosme, M., den Herder, M., Kay, S., Lawson, G., Lojka, B., Palma, J., Pardon, P., Reissig, L., Reubens, B., Prins, E., Vandendriessche, J., & Mantino, A. (2024). Exploring agroforestry limiting factors and digitalization perspectives: insights from a european multi-actor appraisal. *Agroforestry Systems*, 98(7), 2499–2515. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-024-01047-x>
- Tranchina, M., Ripamonti, A., Cella, F., Mantino, A., Rolo, V., Prins, E., Thissen, W., den Herder, M., Hübner, R., Bohdan, L., Cumplido-Marin, L., & Burgess, P. (2023). Deliverable 3.1: Schematic Map of the Agroforestry Value Chain for each Living Lab - Submitted report for the DigitAF project (101059794). 72. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15084250>

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